

On the Coexistence of Quantum and Classical Signal Transmission Over Turbulent FSO Channels

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Abstract—Secure data transmission is essential in today’s world, and quantum key distribution (QKD) is widely recognized as the technology of choice to enable information-theoretical secure symmetric key generation. While optical fibers are typically used as a transmission channel, wireless transmission offers the flexibility to reach every part of the Earth; moreover, for Earth-Satellite QKD, wireless communication naturally becomes a necessity. In this study, we deployed a fiber-wireless optical system that transmitted a 64-QAM 400 Gbps classical signal for high-rate data exchange and a 1 MHz quantum signal for QKD. The impact of turbulence in the quantum system is evaluated by transmitting single-polarization quantum states through a turbulent free-space channel and by calculating the respective intrinsic quantum bit error rate (QBER). From this, we estimate the system’s secret key rate (SKR) and its dependence on turbulence. The effects of atmospheric turbulence on the optical wireless signal were emulated and investigated by using a custom-made atmospheric chamber to induce different turbulent scenarios. The atmospheric chamber allowed us to vary the turbulence in a Rytov variance range from 0.06 to 2.52. The classical signal showed an overall average reliability of 82% for the mentioned turbulence regimes. The results of the quantum signal showed that for Rytov variances up to 1.3, and under the conditions tested, secret key generation is possible, reaching a maximum SKR of 8.7×10^{-4} bits per pulse during the produced turbulence regimes.

Index Terms—coexistence, turbulence, free-space optics, quantum key distribution, secret key rate.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, quantum key distribution (QKD) is a highly mature cryptography method that enables the secret sharing of an encryption key [1]. This is achieved by taking advantage of quantum mechanics that allow the development of unconditionally secure communication protocols by exploiting the non-cloning theorem and the uncertainty principle [2]. QKD has been extensively investigated using optical fiber transmission channels reaching high key generation rates

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over long distances [3], [4]. While fiber optics provide one quasi-ideal transmission channel for QKD, in some cases its deployment can be difficult, being hindered by geographical constraints, licensing, or deployment time. Free-space optics (FSO) based QKD overcomes these issues by seamlessly bringing the portability of wireless transmission to QKD systems. Therefore, FSO-based QKD has been a matter of increasing interest given the wide range of applications, e.g., for satellite communications [5], or for data-center security [6]. For these applications, among others, it is advantageous to achieve coexistence between the classical and QKD signals, thereby exploiting the already existing classical communications infrastructure. Despite the numerous advantages of FSO already evidenced by classical communications, such as portability, reduced costs [7], high data rates [8], fast deployment [9], security, unlimited bandwidth, and working in an unlicensed wireless spectrum [10], this technology has the drawback of being impacted by a time varying channel (due to atmospheric turbulence and weather) [11]. Therefore, to work towards the implementation of FSO-QKD systems, these challenges must be deeply analysed defining operating regimes as a function of understandable metrics of turbulence or weather conditions.

Worldwide quantum security can be achieved by combining mature secure protocols, such as DV-QKD, with the widely deployed optical communications infrastructure; moreover, expanding this network and adding wireless capabilities using FSO, can be a crucial step in achieving secure communications everywhere [12]. For the QKD integration into existent networks, it is important to develop systems in which QKD coexists with classical data transmission systems, enabling a secure high-rate data transmission. However, the integration of QKD into an optical classical network can be challenging, with a primary conditioner being the high-power of classical signals compared to quantum signals, which can contaminate the quantum signal, compromising its successful transmission [13].

In contrast with the well studied fiber based QKD approach, FSO systems come with other impairments, such as pointing errors and turbulence, that must be considered and deeply analysed. Regarding FSO-QKD transmissions, in [14], a theoretical study of indoor wireless quantum-classical transmissions is performed for several QKD protocols, while in [15] a theoretical analysis of a fiber-wireless scenario is performed. Both studies suggest the viability of such transmissions. Multiple experimental demonstrations of FSO-QKD have already been performed, namely in [16], where a high-

dimensional entanglement-based QKD transmission is carried out over an outdoor 1.2 km FSO channel, achieving 20 kcps despite the harsh wavefront distortion caused by atmospheric turbulence. In that regard, it is important to mention that high-dimensional QKD is a promising approach towards free-space QKD, given its potential resilience to noise [17], with the prospect of improving secret key rates (SKRs) [18]. In [19], another experimental QKD demonstration is reported over a 3 km outdoor FSO channel, achieving a low error rate of 1.7% even under strong atmospheric turbulence. For such transmissions, performing a thorough characterization of the FSO channel is essential to enable its deployment and understand the results. In that regard, in [20], the authors demonstrate that the behaviour of quantum and classical signals in turbulence is strongly correlated, thereafter proposing a novel approach to characterize the quantum channel using classical light. Moreover, the effect of pointing accuracy and channel spacing was studied in [13] on a coexisting quantum and classical signal using wavelength division multiplexing (WDM), demonstrating that both aspects strongly impact the QKD performance. Moreover, the effect of turbulence was studied in [21] using a Spatial Light Modulator (SLM), which allowed to study the effect of three discrete turbulence scenarios. This work confirmed the impact of turbulence on a QKD signal. However, SLMs are polarization dependent, compromising their use in the study of turbulence in polarization-encoding QKD systems. Additionally, the dynamic sub-ms effects of atmospheric turbulence can be difficult to emulate using a SLM, given their limited operation frequency. This way, to the best of our knowledge, few experiments presented in the literature show the effect of turbulence on FSO QKD systems. Moreover, no experiments assess classic and DV-QKD coexistent transmissions with realistic atmospheric turbulence, i.e., with an FSO channel with a dynamic response.

While outdoor FSO demonstrations, such as those presented in [16] and [19], are susceptible to atmospheric conditions, they are also affected by the different impairments mentioned above, so it can be difficult to isolate the effect of atmospheric turbulence for its study. Additionally, demonstrations of how the turbulence affects the signal are limited by the weather conditions on the days and locations of measurement [21]. Given the high dependence between atmospheric turbulence and atmospheric conditions, repeatability can also be difficult to achieve. In this work, to overcome these challenges, and to conduct a sound experiment about the impact of atmospheric turbulence in a quantum-classical FSO system, we use a custom-made atmospheric chamber to emulate the turbulence caused by different conditions in a lab-controlled and repeatable manner. While inducing turbulence in the atmospheric chamber, we monitored the attenuation, and photon counts reaching the single photon detectors (SPDs). This way, the impact of turbulence on the quantum bit error rate (QBER), and SKR in polarization-encoding QKD systems were analysed. These results were obtained during the transmission of a single wavelength 400 Gbps classical optical signal for high-rate data transmission coexisting with a 1 MHz quantum signal for QKD. Results showed that, in the conditions tested, a Rytov variance range of 0.06 to 2.52 was achieved, for

which the classical signal showed an overall average reliability of 82%. While the transmission of the classical signal was seamless for Rytov variances up to about 1.5, the secret key generation is compromised for Rytov variances of 1.3 and upward, overall, with a SKR variation up to 8.7×10^{-4} bits per pulse (bpp), showing the strong impact of turbulence on the quantum signal.

This paper is divided as follows: in Section II, the practical implementation of the method is discussed, including a description of the experimental setup and the atmospheric chamber. In Section III, we present the results that characterize the turbulence of the experiment discussed here. The signal results of the experiment are presented in Section IV, namely, the reliability and QBER results. In Section V, an analysis of the SKR during the experiment is presented. Finally, in Section VI, the conclusions are discussed.

II. QUANTUM-CLASSICAL COEXISTENCE SCENARIO

In this section, we will present a detailed description of the experimental setup employed for the coexistence of the classical and quantum signals. Moreover, the details of implementation and a description of the atmospheric chamber used for the turbulence emulation are also provided. The classical signal corresponds to a high-speed optical signal with coherent detection, whereas the quantum setup emulates a prepare and measure polarization-encoding Discrete-Variable (DV) QKD signal transmission, compatible with the execution of a decoy-state BB84 protocol.

A. Experimental Setup and Implementation

Fig. 1 depicts the experimental setup used to deploy the simultaneous transmission of quantum and classical signals over a turbulent FSO channel. The quantum signal is generated at the quantum transmitter (QTx) using an external cavity laser (ECL) emitting at 1547.72 nm. The signal is modulated by a Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM) as a 1 MHz pulsed signal. The modulated signal is then filtered by Optical Filter 1 (OF1) to remove out-of-band noise and attenuated by a variable optical attenuator (VOA) to an appropriate number of photons per pulse. The coexistence of the classical and quantum signals in the optical channel was implemented with the help of two optical circulators (OCs), in a counter-propagating configuration. When compared to a WDM approach, the employment of OCs facilitates the wavelength selection of the two signals, as well as the filtering of the classical contamination. Note that the choice of a counter-propagation approach was mainly due to restrictions on the availability of lab equipment, namely WDM multiplexing and demultiplexing components with a high isolation, and was not related to any fundamental limitation of a co-propagation configuration. Since the joint propagation takes place in free-space, there is no signal degradation associated with non-linear effects, so a co- or counter-propagation approach should present similar results. At the QTx, the quantum signal enters the OC1 through the I port and exits through the I/O port to the corresponding collimator (C1) (model: Thorlabs F810APC-1550) pointed to a second equal collimator (C2). The FSO

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of the experimental setup for the transmission of a counter-propagating classical and quantum signal through the atmospheric chamber. The insets show: a) the 64 QAM constellation of the classical signal at the CRx DSP; b) the counts measured at the SPDs as a function of the attenuation imposed by the WS; c) the probability distribution of the symbols at the CTx DSP.

path between the two collimators has a length of about 1.5 m, with an atmospheric chamber of 1.2 m to induce turbulence in the FSO link. After the FSO link, the quantum signal enters the second collimator (C2) and follows to the I/O port of OC2, exiting through the O port to the quantum receiver (QRx). After signal filtering, a manual polarization controller (PC) enables to adjust the polarization, before a polarization beam splitter (PBS) is used to divide horizontally polarized photons from vertically polarized ones, directing each to the corresponding SPD (model: ID Quantique ID210). Also, at the QTx, a second signal is generated for synchronization purposes, which is modulated by a second MZM again to produce a 1 MHz frequency. This synchronization signal is connected by fiber to the QRx to give the trigger signal to the SPDs.

At the classical transmitter (CTx) side, a 64 Gbaud signal is generated using probabilistic constellation shaping (PCS) over a 64-QAM template with 20% forward error correction (FEC) overhead, resulting in a net bit-rate of 400 Gbps. This digital signal is also pulse-shaped by a root-raised cosine filter with a 0.02 roll-off. The digital signal is uploaded to an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) with 45 GHz bandwidth and 120 Gsps sampling-rate (model: Keysight M8194A). The AWG is connected to a dual-polarization IQ modulator (IQM) (model: Fujitsu FTM7992HM) with 35 GHz bandwidth that performs optical modulation over an optical carrier (1528.77 nm) generated by another ECL. After optical modulation, the classical signal is amplified by an erbium-doped fiber amplifier (EDFA). To reduce the noise caused by amplification, the signal is filtered by a wave shaper (WS) (model: Finisar WS4000S), serving as a stop band filter in the spectral region of the quantum signal (1547.72 nm). Given the concern regarding a possible leakage from the classical signal to the quantum signal, we have measured the number

of counts registered in the SPDs as a function of the WS’s attenuation. These results are represented in Fig. 1, inset b). For each attenuation value, counts were measured 30 times; individual values are represented as orange circles, while the blue line displays their average. One observes that for attenuation values larger than 40 dB the count rate is mainly given by the dark counts of the detectors, approximately 138 per second. This leads to the conclusion that during the coexistent transmission the filter attenuation should be above 40 dB. Regarding the potential crosstalk associated with the use of optical circulators, we have measured the attenuation between the I and O ports, and between the I/O and I ports, which was above 50 dB for both circulators, representing no significant risk of contaminating the quantum signal.

After the WS, the classical signal enters OC2 through the I port and exits through the I/O port, where the coexistence with the quantum signal starts. After passing through the atmospheric chamber, part of the classical signal (8%) is deviated by a free-space beam splitter (BS), and is focused on a quadrant detector (QD) (model: Thorlabs PDQ30C) by a lens (L). With the information provided by the QD, two motors (model: Thorlabs PIAK10) attached to C2, and controlled by two piezo-controllers (model: Thorlabs KPZ101), enable the beam positioning along the x and y axis for the FSO link alignment. Note that this alignment technique allows for a compensation of the temperature dependent average angular deflection of the optical beam, however, effects such as beam wandering were not compensated for. This was due to the need for faster alignment techniques, such as fast steering mirrors. The other portion of the signal is coupled into the fiber and directed to OC1, where the classical signal enters through the I/O port and exits through the O port to a 1/99 BS. The 1% portion follows to a fast optical power meter (FOPM) and the 99% is directed to the classical receiver (CRx). At the CRx, the

classical signal is amplified by an EDFA with automatic power control and is directed to the coherent receiver (CR). The output of the CR is then digitized and quantized by four real-time oscilloscopes (model: Tektronix DPO77002SX-R3). Afterwards, off-line digital signal processing (DSP) is performed, namely: IQ imbalance compensation, 2×2 constant modulus algorithm (CMA)-based adaptive equalization, frequency and phase recovery, 2×2 least mean squares (LMS) equalization, bit decoding, and normalized generalized mutual information (NGMI) [22] evaluation.

B. Atmospheric Chamber

The atmospheric chamber is equipped with two heaters to induce turbulence through temperature variation, represented in Fig. 2 a) by H1 and H2, and two thermometers to monitor the temperature changes, represented by T1 and T2. As suggested by atmospheric turbulence models, such as the Log-Normal, or Gamma-Gamma, turbulence is caused by temperature or pressure gradients, which is why heaters are used to induce such conditions [23]. The classical and quantum signals are sent through the atmospheric chamber by the two collimators, C1 and C2, located outside of the chamber. To better understand the temperature distribution during the heating of the chamber, an infrared camera was used to take a picture when the temperature registered by T1 reached 50°C , see Fig. 2 b). Notice that the infrared image displays the thermal temperature of the objects' surfaces; therefore, it may not precisely reflect the real temperature inside the chamber but the gradients at their surface. One can see that the highest temperature is encountered at the upper part of the atmospheric chamber, as hot air tends to rise due to its lower density. However, the optical signals are transmitted through the chamber at a lower point, as can be seen in Fig. 2 a) from the height of the collimators. At this height there are several temperature regimes that can be observed, such that higher temperatures are encountered at the edges of the atmospheric chamber while a lower temperature is found at the center of the chamber.

III. TURBULENCE CHARACTERIZATION

In this experiment, the heaters were turned on during 30 minutes, gradually increasing the temperature from 22.6°C to 53.1° (see Fig. 3 a)). Note that Fig. 3 a) shows the temperature variation during the experiment as a function of time, enabling a time correspondence between the results that follow, which are also presented as a function of time. During the experiment, the optical power reaching the receiver side of the atmospheric chamber was measured with the FOPM at a sampling rate of 10^4 Hz, see Fig. 3 b). The received optical power gradually decreases from -24 dBm to -41 dBm, as the turbulence increases. To ensure that the alignment of the FSO channel was correctly performed during the whole experiment, the position of the incident beam on the QD was continuously registered as shown in Fig. 3 c). Given that the X and Y position of the beam is oscillating around the central point with a maximum radial deviation of 0.15 mm, we can conclude that

Fig. 2: a) Photograph of the atmospheric chamber, signalling the location of the two heaters (H1 and H2), the thermometers (T1 and T2), and the collimators (C1 and C2); b) Photograph taken by an infrared camera of the atmospheric chamber showing the heat distribution during the heating process.

some additional losses are present, due to turbulence-induced beam wandering.

To characterize the impact of turbulence over time, the measured received power was divided in blocks of 10 seconds and the pdf was computed for each block. Two atmospheric turbulence models were considered to extract the Rytov variance, σ_l^2 , and the refractive index structure parameter, C_n^2 : the Log-Normal and Gamma-Gamma model described in [23]. Nevertheless, due to the prevailing stronger turbulence felt during the experiment, the Gamma-Gamma model resulted in a lower normalized mean squared error when fitting the experimental data with the theoretical pdf. Example results of this fitting are shown in Fig. 4 a), b), and c). For each data block, the σ_l^2 and the C_n^2 were obtained, see Fig. 4 d).

By comparing Fig. 4 a), b), and c) we can observe that, as expected, the Gamma-Gamma model presents a better fitting of the data in stronger turbulence scenarios. This way, this model becomes the more appropriated one to describe the experienced turbulence-induced power fluctuations. Before the heaters were turned on, i.e., without turbulence, the Rytov variance was close to 3×10^{-4} , corresponding to the baseline Gaussian noise that characterizes the classical optical signal (e.g. due to laser and EDFA noise sources). However, as soon as the temperature started to rise, the Rytov variance showed a sudden increase to about 10^{-1} and then a gradual increase, reaching its maximum, 2.52, at minute 30.5. The increase of

Fig. 3: a) Temperature measured during the experiment by thermometer 1 and thermometer 2, and their average; b) Optical power received by the FOPM; c) X and Y positions of the optical beam reaching the QD during the experiment.

Fig. 4: Pdf of the measured data as a function of the normalized irradiance for: a) minute 3; b) minute 9.3; c) minute 30.5. The red lines represent the fit to the measured data using a Gamma-Gamma model. d) Rytov variance and C_n^2 as a function of time.

the Rytov variance is steeper at the beginning, between minute 2 and 10, which can be explained by a higher temperature gradient during that period.

Overall, the conditions induced by the atmospheric chamber overlie a high range of scenarios, from weak to strong turbulence with the Rytov variance ranging from 0.06 to 2.52. These higher values are characteristic of long distance FSO links (~ 4 km), or extreme turbulent conditions, which can significantly degrade a quantum-classical FSO communication system.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section we will present the experimental results on the performance of the classical and quantum signals during the transmission over an FSO channel with atmospheric turbulence.

A. Performance Results of the Classical Signal

To perform a first assessment of how the classical data transmission quality was affected by the temperature-induced turbulence in the atmospheric chamber, we estimated the NGMI due to its high accuracy estimation of the post-FEC bit error rate [24]. The NGMI was obtained after the CRx

DSP, while the reliability was estimated using a sliding window with a 5 minute block size of NGMI values, using an NGMI threshold of 0.9 to ensure a reasonable coding gap for practical FEC implementations, see Fig. 5. From the obtained in terms of NGMI and reliability, one can see that there is a high dependence between the transmission quality and the turbulence conditions, such that the reliability remains above 90% up to a Rytov variance of 1.3. Notice that the Rytov varied in a range of 0.06 to 2.52 during the experiment, in which for the higher turbulence regime tested (from minute 26 onwards) the reliability is compromised. Nevertheless, an overall average reliability of 82% was achieved for the 30 minutes experiment.

B. Performance Results of the Quantum Signal

For the quantum transmission quality assessment the Intrinsic Quantum Bit Error Ratio (IQBER) was estimated. Since this transmission was performed without polarization modulation, i.e., only one polarization state was used, the quality of the quantum channel is estimated by [2],

$$\text{IQBER}_{\text{exp}} = \frac{C_1}{C_1 + C_2}, \quad (1)$$

where C_1 and C_2 are the counts registered by the SPD1 and SPD2, respectively. For the theoretical IQBER estimation,

Fig. 5: NGMI and reliability as a function of time, showing an average reliability of 82%. The orange dashed line corresponds to the point up to when the reliability remained above 90%, corresponding to a Rytov variance of 1.3.

$\text{IQBER}_{\text{theo}}$, we considered the approach presented in [25], which considers the contributions to the overall QBER of all polarization states used. Given that we only sent one state of polarization, the IQBER can be written as follows [25],

$$\text{IQBER}_{\text{theo}} = \frac{1}{p_{\text{click}}} \left(p_{\text{dc}}(e_0 - e_d) + e_d(1 - (1 - p_{\text{dc}})e^{-\mu\eta_{\text{sys}}}) \right), \quad (2)$$

where p_{click} is the overall click probability at the receiver side, given by $p_{\text{click}} = p_{\text{det}} + p_{\text{dc}} - p_{\text{det}}p_{\text{dc}}$, with p_{dc} being the dark count probability, and p_{det} being the detection probability given by $p_{\text{det}} = 1 - \exp(-\eta_{\text{sys}}\mu)$ [26]. The system efficiency η_{sys} is given by $\eta_{\text{sys}} = \eta_{\text{ch}}\eta_{\text{rx}}\eta_{\text{det}}$, composed by the channel efficiency, η_{ch} , the QRx efficiency, η_{rx} , and the detection efficiency of the SPDs, η_{det} . The other parameter needed for the calculation of p_{det} is the average number of photons per pulse, μ . In (1), the e_0 parameter corresponds to the errors due to dark counts, which is assumed to be $\frac{1}{2}$, and e_d to the probability of a photon going to the wrong detector due to polarization misalignments.

The two IQBER estimations, $\text{IQBER}_{\text{exp}}$ and $\text{IQBER}_{\text{theo}}$,

Fig. 6: Experimental and theoretical IQBER as a function of the dynamic attenuation of the FSO channel.

are represented in Fig. 6 as a function of the channel attenuation, γ . For the representation of the $\text{IQBER}_{\text{theo}}$, the following parameter values were considered: $p_{\text{dc}} = 2.5 \times 10^{-5}$, $\mu = 0.8$ photons per pulse, $\eta_{\text{det}} = 25\%$, and $e_d = 1.8\%$, which corresponds to the first IQBER value measured. Notice that the efficiency of the channel was obtained by computing the attenuation, γ , using the received optical power measurements shown in Fig. 3 b), such that $\eta_{\text{ch}} = 10^{-\gamma/10}$. Similarly, η_{rx} was obtained by the same expression, however, considering a fixed loss accounting for the receiver and alignment losses. From Fig. 6, one can see that $\text{IQBER}_{\text{exp}}$ follows the tendency of $\text{IQBER}_{\text{theo}}$, however, with fluctuations that might occur due to the power fluctuations observed in Fig. 3 b). The vertical shift between the experimental and the theoretical data can be explained by polarization drift occurring during the transmission and due to the movement of the piezo inertia actuators initialized for the FSO link alignment, while for the theoretical curve the contribution due to the polarization contrast was considered constant ($e_d = 1.8\%$).

V. SECRET KEY RATE ANALYSIS

For the performance analysis of the QKD system, the SKR is a good figure of merit to consider. Here, we present an estimation of the system's SKR for the above described atmospheric turbulence. For this estimation, we used the asymptotic approximation of the SKR presented in [25], which considers the implementation of a decoy-state BB84 protocol,

$$R \geq q \left(Q_1(1 - h(e_{1,\text{phase}})) - p_{\text{click}}f_{\text{EC}}h(\text{IQBER}_{\text{theo}}) \right) \quad (3)$$

where q is the efficiency of the protocol, Q_1 is the gain of the single photon states, given by $Q_1 = \mu e^{(-\mu)}Y_1$, with $Y_1 = 1 - (1 - p_{\text{dc}})(1 - \eta_{\text{sys}})$, $e_{1,\text{phase}}$ is the phase error rate of the single photon states which was considered to be $\text{IQBER}_{\text{theo}}$. In (3), the function $h(\cdot)$ represents the binary Shannon entropy, and f_{EC} corresponds to the error correction efficiency.

Notice that for the SKR estimation, the detection probability, p_{det} , needed to calculate p_{click} was obtained by $p_{\text{det}} = 1 - \exp(-\eta_{\text{ch}}\eta_{\text{rx}}\eta_{\text{det}}\mu)$, considering the contribution of the dynamic channel attenuation caused by the FSO channel with atmospheric turbulence, the efficiency of the receiver, and the efficiency of the SPDs [27]. The channel attenuation was obtained from Fig. 3 b), similarly to the $\text{QBER}_{\text{theo}}$ computation described above. The parameters considered for the SKR estimation were as follows: $\mu = 0.5$ photons per pulse, $q = 1/2$, $p_{\text{dc}} = 2.5 \times 10^{-5}$, $\eta_{\text{det}} = 0.08$, $\eta_{\text{rx}} = 0.1$, and $f_{\text{EC}} = 1.16$.

The results obtained for the SKR, in bps, are shown in Fig. 7 a) as a function of time together with the average received power, and in Fig. 7 b) as a function of the Rytov variance. In Fig. 7 a) one can see that about 22 minutes into the experiment, denoted by the blue zone, the attenuation induced by the turbulence is too high, preventing the generation of secret keys. Moreover, in Fig. 7 b), one observes an abrupt decay of the SKR for large values of Rytov variance. Nevertheless, it was shown that under the induced turbulence values, the SKR went to a maximum value of 8.7×10^{-4} bps.

Fig. 7: a) Estimated SKR and channel attenuation as a function of time; b) estimated SKR as a function of the Rytov variance. The estimated SKR was calculated following equation (3).

Note that the SKR, in bits per second, can be obtained by multiplying R , in bps, by the repetition rate. It is important to mention that the SPD specifications have a major impact on the SKR, and therefore on the point at which the SKR is lost. Therefore, it is essential to find a trade-off between the efficiency of the detectors and the dark count rate. Table I shows a comparison of the quantum and classical transmission performances, with an estimation of the FSO channel distance using the Rytov variance expression from [23], assuming a C_n^2 of 10^{-14} . This extrapolation allows us to understand the role of dynamic effects, such as scintillation and beam wandering, in classical and quantum FSO transmission systems. However, the geometrical losses related to link losses and the beam divergence are not considered. For example, in [28], a 1.8 km field trial was performed which estimated Rytov variances of around 10^{-2} , and C_n^2 values of around 2×10^{-16} . In Table I one can see that the SKR goes to zero faster than the decrease of reliability. The value of Rytov variance that gives the upper bound for a possible key distribution corresponds to approximately 2.31 km in this scenario.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the simultaneous transmission of a classical and a quantum signal over the same FSO channel was achieved in a counter-propagating manner. By monitoring the received

TABLE I: Classical and quantum systems performance correspondence with the estimated link distance for a C_n^2 of 10^{-14} .

σ_t^2	0.11	0.50	0.92	1.48	2.07	2.52
SKR (bps)	5.4×10^{-4}	9.3×10^{-5}	5.0×10^{-6}	0	0	0
Reliab. (%)	100	93	93	87	29	13
L_p (km)	0.72	1.65	2.31	2.99	3.59	4.00

power at the CRx, it was possible to estimate the turbulence regime induced by the temperature variations and analyse its effect on the classical and quantum signals. Due to the use of an atmospheric chamber, we were able to induce a large variety of conditions, with the Rytov variance ranging from 0.06 to 2.52. Despite the wide range of turbulence strengths felt during the experiment it is important to notice that the same chamber can be used to induce an even larger variety of turbulence felt by changing parameters such as the beam size. Notice that the goal of inducing such strong turbulence in the FSO channel was also to emulate longer transmission distances. Under normal atmospheric conditions, i.e., considering a C_n^2 of 10^{-14} , the atmospheric chamber allowed us to test the signal transmission under turbulences corresponding to small link distances up to 4 km links. Emulating such a range of link distances allowed us to determine the point at which the signal for QKD is lost, i.e., it is no longer possible to generate secret keys. The classical signal transmission quality was assessed by calculating the NGMI and the reliability. These metrics showed that the transmission remained seamless up to a Rytov variance of 1.3, showing a reliability above 90%. The overall average reliability achieved over the period analysed was 82%. With respect to the quantum signal transmission, an IQBER and SKR evaluation was performed. The system experimental IQBER started at 1.8% and its average increased almost up to 20%, which is related to the preponderance of the dark counts in the strong turbulence regime. As for the SKR, it was shown that after about 22 minutes of induced turbulence (Rytov variance of ~ 1.3), the secret key generation is no longer possible, which is associated to the high attenuation imposed by the turbulence. The set of results presented in this work demonstrates the feasibility of simultaneous classical and quantum transmission over a turbulent FSO channel, paving the way for a real and integrated implementation of these systems.

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